

MIT ART, DESIGN AND TECHNOLOGY UNIVERSITY
MIT School of Bioengineering Sciences & Research

7th INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE
ON
RECENT TRENDS IN BIOENGINEERING
(ICRTB 2024)

January 19-20, 2024

ABSTRACTS

MIT School of
**Bioengineering Sciences
& Research**

Breathe Life into Engineering Career!

MIT-ADT
UNIVERSITY
PUNE, INDIA

A Leap Towards The World Class Education

PP-002

Unlocking the Potential of *Clostridium butyricum* ARI-I: Genomic Insights and Safety Assessment for Probiotic Applications

Advika M. Dhanorkar¹, Shilpa Wagh², Neelam G. Kapse³ and Prashant K. Dhakephalkar³

¹PES Modern College of Arts, Science and Commerce, Shivajinagar, Pune-411005, Maharashtra, India

²Hi Tech BioSciences India Ltd., Research & Development Centre, Pune- 411038, Maharashtra, India

³Agharkar Research Institute, G. G. Agarkar Road, Pune- 411004, Maharashtra, India

Abstract: Antibiotic resistance is a serious global health problem, spurring the quest for new infection-combating techniques. Probiotics, known for their potential to improve gut health and boost the immune system, have garnered significant attention. The limited gastroenteric survival of conventional probiotics such as *Lactobacillus* and *Bifidobacterium*, on the other hand, underscores the need to investigate alternative probiotic bacterial species. Hence, the present study was undertaken to explore the probiotic propensity of spore-forming *Clostridium butyricum* through genome analysis. The genome sequence of *C. butyricum* ARI-I was examined and annotated for molecular mechanisms related to probiosis. Comparative genomics of ARI-I using Eztaxon-ANI, GGDC-DDH, and BRIG analysis with seven publicly available reference genomes of *C. butyricum* indicated a resemblance between them. Functional annotation using the RAST platform predicted the excellent gut adaptive features of ARI-I, like multisubunit F0-F1 ATPases, Na⁺-H⁺ antiporters, and the fibronectin-binding protein-encoding gene for adhesion. Genome mapping also displayed the ability of ARI-I to produce compounds advantageous for the host (folate, bacteriocins), to release antioxidative enzymes against free radicals, and to metabolize lactose potentially harmful to lactose intolerants. The strain also demonstrated a positive effect on reducing cholesterol levels, proving to be a potential candidate for food and pharmaceutical applications. Furthermore, the *in silico* analysis predicted ARI-I as a non-human pathogen devoid of transferable antibiotic resistance or virulent genes, proving its safety as a probiotic.

MIT School of Bioengineering Sciences & Research

Bioengineering is a multidisciplinary field that has gained immense importance in the global scenario. MIT School of Bioengineering Sciences & Research is a constituent unit of MIT Art, Design and Technology University that aims to prepare students for ambitious careers in bioengineering by imparting education and hands-on training through project-based learning. The school helps in introducing students to the world of untapped opportunities in biology using engineering skills. The school envisions to empower India to become a leader in Bioengineering research, development and manufacturing sectors. It offers B. Tech. (Bioengineering), Int. M. Tech. (Bioengineering), M. Tech. (Environmental Bioengineering), M.Sc (Industrial Biotechnology) and Ph.D Programs in Biotechnology, Biomedical Engineering, Bioinformatics and Biomaterials. The super-specialized courses include Pharmaceutical Engineering, Synthetic Biology, Big Data Analytics, Biosensors and IoT, Biomedical Imaging, Biomechanics, Nano-Biotechnology, Robotics, Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence, Environmental bioengineering, etc. The school is equipped with state-of-art laboratories for carrying out high-end research and innovative product development.

Rajbaug, Next to Hadapsar, Loni Kalbhor, Pune 412201, India.

+91 744 7444 027 / 28 | +91 914 6051 841 / 42

www.mitbio.edu.in / icrtb@mituniversity.edu.in

ISBN 978-93-6039-051-8

9 789360 390518